

Site: SPHINX TEMPLE Season GS 79-80

Area: N. COLONNADE Square R16 Locus Number 46

Progress of Excavation On 7/I/80 (4a) and (4b) broken through to (4c) together (and some of (4a) probably still with it.) 4b originally called 4a - but 10/I/80 clear it is separate level and not a lens. To balk trimming corner ^{NE} R16, 4b - LIGHT BUFF CLAY-GYPSUM ^{or mod} CLEARED separately (50% of it remains as only small part broken through yesterday.) // 4b Cleared to trimmed Balk.

Locus Description LIGHT BUFF CLAY-GYPSUM(?)
While distinct, 4b does seem to be lensed w/ darker tan clay similar to 4a. and this seems to phase into 4c

Location in Square NE Corner R16 as in excavation edge, "mound" of 4-4a-4b, 4c,

Under Locus 4a DARK TAN CLAY Over Locus 4c Brown sand-stone Rubble

Locus Dimensions 3-6 cm thick

Levels _____

Analysis of non-artifactual materials _____